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MECHANICAL ENGINEERING STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF THE QUALITY OF WORK AFFORDANCES DURING WORK PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The quality of work experience that is available to engineering students as part of the formal academic programme has considerable influence on their employability outcomes. Despite this, the factors and processes through which they exert their influence have not been fully understood. This paper describes a study that sought to explain what influences the quality of work affordances and how this influence is produced. The study collected qualitative data from mechanical engineering students using interviews and documents. It then analysed the data using thematic analysis and synthesis. It found that the learning environment and the industry mentor influence the quality of work affordances that students experience. It also found that interactions between industry mentor as work supervisor and teacher and an enabling learning environment tended to produce broad and meaningful work affordances. Conversely, industry mentor as work supervisor only and constraining learning environments led to the affordance of work of narrow scope. Understanding of these processes would empower universities to influence the meaningfulness of the work placement experiences of their students.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Work placement can provide students with personal knowledge of the workplace, generic skills, attitudes and behaviours that facilitate a smooth transition into employment. However, ensuring that all students who go through work placement get appropriate work experience is challenging. Rayner and Theo [1] provide many examples of what can go wrong with work placement, such as students being used as cheap labour and being assigned work that is not related to their qualification. Nevison et al. [2] explain that exposure to meaningful work is an essential factor of work placement experiences that contribute to the enhancement of students' functional capabilities. They found that the learning environment has a significant influence on the perceived meaningfulness of afforded work placement. Similarly, Kramer-Simpson [3] found that the quality and attitude of an industry mentor influence the meaningfulness of work.

Unfortunately, these two studies, and most other previous studies, consider the influence of organisational environment and industry mentor factors in isolation from each other. Therefore, it remains unclear as to how these factors interact and how their interaction might influence the quality of afforded work. Consideration of the interactions of the factors in addition to their individual influence on work affordances is essential in developing a clearer picture of the mechanism influencing the quality of work affordances. To allow for interaction of the factors, work placement needs to be considered as a conceptual system. A conceptual system is "a network of multiple variables that are connected through causal relationship and expresses some sort of behaviour, which can only be characterised through observation as a whole" [4]. Work placement can be considered a system that is intended to transform students who have theoretical knowledge of engineering concepts into students who have occupational competency and self-efficacy in engineering; in other words, work-ready. This paper sought to explain how mechanical engineering students' perception of their organisational environment and industry mentor factors influence how they perceive the quality of their work affordances. Understanding this is crucial in designing and implementing work placement programs in a manner that promotes student employability.

2 METHODOLOGY

The research presented in this paper followed a qualitative multi-case study approach. This approach is appropriate for an investigation such as this that sought to explain the variables and processes influencing the quality of work affordances by drawing on the perceptions of the participants themselves

2.1 Research participants

The study collected qualitative data from thirty-four participants, mechanical engineering students from a South African university of technology who were undergoing year-long placements. Thirty-two participants were placed at companies within one province. The remaining two participants were placed in a different

province. Only two participants had previous exposure to work experience, one as a sales administrator and the other as an engineering drawing instructor.

2.2 Data collection

After obtaining institutional ethics approval, qualitative data was collected from the participants using semi-structured interviews, and from the examination of their work placement logbooks and evidence portfolios.

2.3 Data analysis

The study used a qualitative data analysis process that combined Bryman's [5] generic thematic analysis approach and the interactive data analysis process developed by Miles, Huberman and Saldana [6]. The steps that were followed in the data analysis are illustrated in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1: Steps that were followed during qualitative data analysis

The analysis started with the thematic analysis. This was followed by thematic synthesis, which comprised intra-case and inter-case comparison using matrix coding, comparison diagrams and hierarchical charts. The thematic synthesis allowed the researcher to discover relationships between the subthemes. These were modelled using causal loop diagrams using procedures that were developed by Yearworth and White [7].

3 FINDINGS

Thematic analysis identified three themes representing aspects of work placement experiences that formed the work affordance system. Each theme had several constituent subthemes, representing various attributes. The remainder of this section presents the findings related to the three components of work affordance system.

3.1 Theme one: the learning environment

The findings show that the students categorised their experiences of their environment as either enabling or constraining. They considered their learning environment to be enabling if they had access to broad and meaningful work and close guidance. On the contrary, the students considered their learning environments to be constraining if they filled actual job positions, had access to work of narrow scope, had limited access to guidance and if their environments had a low tolerance for work errors.

The attributes of constraining environments signalled minimal allowance for activities that facilitated student learning and an inclination to structure students' work affordances to meet organisational goals. This inclination resulted in students filling actual job positions which severely constrained their learning and curtailed their exposure to task diversity. Ordinarily, this might have been beneficial, but because of their lack of work experience, most students were assigned low-skill, low-risk assignments which offered little university-practice integration.

3.2 Theme two: the industry mentor

The findings suggest that the students considered their industry mentors' actions to be the most significantly influential aspect of the learning environments. They believed that their industry mentors exercised control over access to work and participation opportunities that were available in the learning environment. An industry mentor's ability to function in this role was dependent on that mentor's capacity and availability. Mentor capacity refers to a mentor's ability to perform mentoring functions in a manner that facilitates efficacious workplace student learning. Mentor availability refers to the ease with which students might access guidance from mentors. The guidance entailed giving direction to the students about what they needed to do, allowing them to observe their co-workers in action and participating side by side with the students in work activities.

The findings showed that most high-capacity mentors were from the management echelons of the host companies. These mentors had the power to allocate meaningful work to the students. Some students reported that their mentors diverted work from themselves or other workers to their students to expose them to a diverse range of work assignments. With most high-capacity mentors, there was the challenge of availability. However, some mentors were able to compensate for their unavailability by delegating some of the mentoring responsibilities to their subordinates.

Students reported that they struggled to complete most work activities on their own. In most cases, high-availability mentors – who were often the students' immediate supervisors – were available to provide guidance. Unfortunately, with most high-availability mentors, there was the challenge of providing their protégés with a broad scope of work. These mentors did not often have the authority to assign students to other departments, even when they thought that the students would benefit from such an assignment.

Most participants spoke of their mentors in two ways: as if they were teachers or only as supervisors. These two perceived postures reflect an inherent tension that exists in workplaces. Students' recollections of the placement experiences suggested continuous contestation between learning and working, which presented itself in the mentor-to-student interactions. When the mentor was positioned as a supervisor, productivity was prioritised over learning. In contrast, when the mentor was positioned as a teacher, the students' learning was prioritised over operational gains, or at least these needs were considered together.

3.3 Theme three: quality of work affordances

The work that was available to students during work placement varied in terms of scope and meaningfulness. Some work affordances were broad and meaningful, whereas others were of narrow scope. Some students reported that they were exposed to diverse work assignments that added value to their placement company, work that would ordinarily be performed by technicians or engineers. Also, the students were exposed to non-technical work such as interacting with contractors and clients, which improved their generic skills such as problem-solving, teamwork, leading work teams and communication. Such broad exposure assisted the students to appreciate the nature of engineering practice. It also gave students confidence that they would be successful in their future employment.

Unfortunately, other students reported that they were afforded work of narrow scope that was based on operational considerations rather than their learning needs. Most of this work tended to be monotonous and of low-responsibility such as operating various production equipment, inspecting the quality of products, doing administrative work and performing artisan-level tasks. The students considered these tasks token and not aligned to their future roles as technicians. As a result, they developed low occupational self-efficacy and became worried about their work readiness. It was found that in some cases, repetition of work tasks was beneficial in that it facilitated task proficiency. Some students who were placed in a single department for the entire placement period developed high self-efficacy. These students had performed work that was of value to their placement company and which aligned to their perceived identity as future engineering practitioners.

3.4 The work affordance system

The analysis suggests that the attributes of the themes represented their variation. Thus, they were identified as variables; in total, six variables were identified. The identified variables are shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. The variables that form the work affordance system and its outcome

System component/outcome	Variables (scale)
Learning environment	Enabling /constraining
The industry mentor	As teacher /as supervisor/ as teacher and supervisor High capacity /low capacity High availability /low availability
Quality of work affordances	Meaningful/token Broad/narrow scope

The intra-case and inter-case comparison uncovered relations among some of the variables shown in *Table 1*. Besides, associations among the learning environment, mentor capacity, mentor posture and quality of work affordances were identifiable from the student's recollections of their experiences. For example, the students believed that when their mentors positioned themselves as supervisors, their actions were directed at either ensuring that the students fulfilled some operational demand such as replacing staff who had resigned or filling positions that had arisen owing to increased work demands. They suggested that this led to their exposure to work of narrow scope. In addition, the association of mentor posture and the learning environment was reflected in how a change in learning environment produced a change in mentor posture. Thus, the mentor posture was not static. It was responsive to the prevailing environment within the workplace. In some cases, a change in workplace conditions influenced mentor posture. In this study, the most common change in workplace conditions was staff shortages due to resignations.

The study found further associations among other variables. When all the associations were mapped using qualitative systems dynamics modelling, the work affordance system shown in *Fig. 2*.

Fig. 2: The work affordance system: its variables and their associations

Fig. 2 suggests that the likelihood of an enabling learning environment increased with an increase in mentor capacity and mentor availability, i.e. a feedback loop. High mentor capacity and mentor availability facilitated an enabling learning environment. Fig. 2 further suggests that the persistence of the enabling learning environment depended on mentor posture. If the industry mentor adopted and continued functioning as both teacher and work supervisor, the enabling learning environment was sustained through the functioning of the enabling sub-loop. In case of a change in the industry mentor's posture to that of supervisor or teacher only, the effectiveness of the enabling learning environment was compromised.

It can be seen from Fig. 2 that continued affordance of meaningful work was dependent on the presence of an enabling learning environment sustaining the mentor posture as both teacher and work supervisor. In contrast, Fig 2 also suggests that limited mentor capacity and availability increases the likelihood of a constraining learning environment. It suggests that once formed, a constraining learning environment influences the industry mentor to adopt the posture of supervisor only. When this happens, the interaction of these two elements results in students being afforded work of narrow scope that do not address their learning needs.

4 DISCUSSION

This paper explored how the systemic behaviour of variables influences the quality of work affordances that are available to mechanical engineering students during work placement. It was expected that the learning environment [2], the industry mentor [3] and student characteristics [8] would form part of this system. However, the findings show that only the learning environment and industry mentors explicitly influence the

quality of work affordances and each other. This finding does not mean that student's agency is irrelevant. The findings showed that students solicited work and guidance from their industry mentors more than from any other source. By going through their industry mentors, the students used collective constructional agency to indirectly influencing the quality of work affordances [8]. For example, in Fig. 2, the return path from mentor as supervisor and teacher to enabling learning environment has elements of the students' participation in the work affordance system, even though their influence is mediated by their industry mentors.

Another issue that arose from the findings is the significance of the industry mentor's influence. The findings show that the industry mentor's ability to act as supervisor and teacher was an antecedent of meaningful work affordances. The students believed that the afforded work was meaningful if it were similar to that performed by their co-workers. They wanted their mentors to give them the responsibility to perform such tasks. However, the students needed to be provided support when it appears that they would not be able to perform these practitioner-level tasks without support. Kramer-Simpson [3] referred to this as 'contingent scaffolding', giving the students an illusion of choice and responsibility, while observing from afar to ensure that the students learn from the activities and also meet the requirements of the workplace. It was this contingent scaffolding that necessitated the additional attributes of enabling learning environments that had moderate tolerance of work errors because as novices, student performance is slow and prone to errors [9].

Effective execution of industry mentors' role as supervisor and teacher required support from co-workers. The industry mentors would not provide contingent scaffolding to their students all the time. They needed support from co-workers to discreetly observe the students and provide feedback to them on how the students were doing. This collaborates the findings by Eames and Bell [10] that suggest that work placement learning is socially situated, hence the actions of co-workers that can not be ignored. Learning during work placement requires occupational socialisation that goes beyond the industry-mentor-student interactions. Therefore, other people in the workplace need to know the reasons for and support the presence of work placement students in the workplace. This is consistent with Lave and Wenger's [11] view of learning as legitimate peripheral participation in a social community and whose success depends on the actions of their entire community.

The awareness of the significance of the industry mentor's influence on the meaningfulness of afforded work provides an opportunity for universities to influence the quality of their students' work placement experiences. Universities would provide training to new industry mentors to enable them to provide authentic work to students and support them with contingent scaffolding. Such training would also be provided to industry mentors as an intervention when work placement coordinators consider an ongoing student work placement to be going in the wrong direction. Although industry mentors training has not been tried in work placement programs

that are offered by South African universities of technology, literature from other countries suggest that the training would enhance the quality of mentoring that students receive. For instance, in their study of teacher education mentors, Lejonberg, Elstad and Christophersen [12] found that training workplace mentors would enable them to understand their roles better and to develop awareness and skills that would enable them to adopt a multi-faceted approach to their mentoring.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper explained the mechanism that determines the quality of work affordances during work placement. It showed the quality of work affordance is an outcome of dynamic interactions of factors relating to industry mentors and the learning environments. It further explained that there is a reciprocal influence between the industry mentor and the learning environment. The awareness of reciprocal influence presents an opportunity for universities to influence the quality of work affordance that is available by devising training programs for industry mentors that would enable them to adopt appropriate posture. It also suggests that it is possible, through targeted interventions, for universities to change the trajectory of work placements that seem to be going wrong by promoting appropriate mentor posture.

The findings of this study are especially relevant for work placement programs for mechanical engineering students in South Africa. However, the finding that industry mentors are crucial to the provision of meaningful work placement experiences is equally relevant to other countries with comparable higher education systems. Therefore, subsequent studies should investigate whether the systemic consideration of work affordances and the emergent outcomes about the quality thereof applies to other academic disciplines and in different economies.

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